

Artistic Psychology as a Literary Term

Rajabov Akhtam Uktamovich

Independent researcher,

Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management

rajabovaxtam178@gmail.com

Abstract: : the article discusses and analyzes the emergence of a psychological image in Uzbek literature, the principles of psychologism, concepts and categories of psychologism in literary studies, psychological stimuli, the emergence of a psychological school, psychological artistic images.

Keywords — literary studies, psychologism, artistic image, concept, principle, analysis, character.

INTRODUCTION.

Although the concepts related to spirituality and psychologism have been recognized in the scientific circles of Uzbek literary studies since the middle of the 20th century, the analysis and interpretation of the psyche of the individual has taken a leading place in the classical literature of the East and the works of its representatives. It is also true that in Uzbek literature alone, Alisher Navoi revealed many secrets of the human psyche in his lyrical works and epic epics, and that the great thinker of Eastern literature used various tools and methods of artistic psychology.[1]

Although the concepts related to spirituality and psychologism have been recognized in the scientific circles of Uzbek literary studies since the middle of the 20th century, the analysis and interpretation of the psyche of the individual has taken a leading place in the classical literature of the East and the works of its representatives. It is true that in Uzbek literature alone, Alisher Navoi revealed many secrets of the human psyche in his lyrical works and epic epics, and that the great thinker of Eastern literature used various tools and methods of artistic psychology. However, according to the opinions of some literary scholars, the issue of artistic psychologism in literary studies has not yet been fully theoretically substantiated and "semantically not clear enough in the science of literary studies".[2]

In scientific sources on literary studies, three main principles of artistic psychology are distinguished - analytical principle, typological principle and dynamic principle. In the dynamic principle, the psyche of the hero is expressed through his actions, gestures and facial expressions, his behavior and words depending on different life situations. "Essentially, this is similar to the method of revealing the psyche of the characters of a dramatic work. Therefore, the dynamic principle is sometimes described as a dramaturgical method of psychological analysis. In the typological principle, the psyche of the image is described in connection with the conditions of the environment that formed and surrounded it. The analytical principle describes the feelings, dynamics of thoughts, inner experiences, thinking and reasoning of the hero. "In this, another feeling grows out of one feeling, another thought grows out of one thought, they complement each other, change

in terms of quality". For this reason, some researchers call it a form of "dialectic of the heart".

It should be noted that the author can use the three forms mentioned above together, complementing each other completely, in revealing the character of the artistic image and its psyche in detail. In such cases, one of the principles is active and leading, and the other two serve to complement it. In general, it should be noted that the concept of "character" occupies a leading place in most of the studies of artistic psychology. The reason is that although research in this direction is related to the science of literary studies, on the one hand, it is also directly related to the science of psychology. It is based on the intersection of these two areas. This, in turn, requires clarifying the concept of "character" both from the point of view of literary studies and psychology.

When determining the place of psychology in the system of concepts and categories of literary studies, first of all, it is necessary to consider that psychology is a description of the inner world of characters, and in turn, the images of characters belong to the objective imagery [4.181] of the artistic form in literature, or, as A.B. Esin says, the depicted world. we must admit that it has been accepted. In this sense, psychologism is expressed as a special quality of artistic form. At the same time, in some works, that is, in psychological novels, psychologism can be a dominant style. A. in the field of the depicted universe. B. Yesin distinguishes three possible stylistic dominants: in which works it is psychologism, in which it is plot-like, in which it is narrative [5, 179].] In this case, not only the characters' images, but also other artistic forms all elements, i.e. the depicted world, artistic speech, composition, are subject to psychologism, as they form an aesthetic unity - style. In this regard, A. B. Yesin defines psychologism as "methodical unity (integrity)". [6.73] In this way, the artistic system of psychologism can cover all three aspects of the artistic form and be presented with various artistic means and methods, in which works it is the dominant method. It should not be forgotten that although the artistic form is a special quality, "psychology is not separate from the content of the artistic work". , the content animating it is of decisive importance". [4. 429-430]

Psychologism is nothing but a detailed and deep psychological description. Since the term "psychological image" used by some researchers is synonymous with the term

"psychologism". In the research, it was proved that psychological analysis is a unique phenomenon in the history of world artistic thinking based on the classification of psychological analysis tools. Accordingly, the third part of the first chapter was devoted to the study of "Principles and methods of mental analysis, tools of psychological imaging". Literary scholars suggest dividing the main forms of psychoanalysis into two: "inner" (direct form) and "external" (indirect, superficial) forms. According to L. Ya. Ginzburg, "Psychological analysis is carried out in the form of the direct form of the author's reflections or self-analysis of the characters. And indirectly - their meaningful actions and gestures are analytically interpreted by the reader who has been prepared by the author". [8.347.] I.V. Strakhov describes the forms of mental analysis as describing the characters "inside", that is, "which emerges with the help of inner speech, images and imaginations in memory. by understanding the inner world of persons in action" and "apparently" means to describe, "expressive specificity of speech, speech and mimic behavior by the writer - by interpreting the expression of the inside on the outside" [9.4]

In general, agreeing with I.V. Strakhov's thoughts, A.B. Esin considers it the third form called "summarnooboznachayushiy": "to tell the reader about the thoughts and feelings of the character in the inner world, suggests filling in with a brief explanation.[10.13]

It seems that the use of spatial symbols in distinguishing forms of psychoanalysis (inside-outside) creates confusion related to the intermingling of narrative stages, subject-object relations. V. Gudonene, like a number of other researchers (I. V. Strakhov, A. B. Esin), classifies the methods of psychological imaging according to the boundaries of the literature of the 19th century. The very concept of "forms of mental analysis" forcibly directs the analysis of psychologism in a realistic modification (explanation of character). In general, the proposed classifications cannot fully reflect the literary reality. O.N. Osmolovsky's words about the "psychological method (manner)" given in consideration of the lyrical, dramatic and epic forms of 20th century literature are not in vain.

The traditional methods of psychological text are sufficiently fully and widely covered in scientific researches and educational manuals created for psychological analysis in works of art.[11] In particular, psychological detailing, portraiture methods, storytelling forms (internal and external speech of the character, dialogue, author's commentary, etc.) have been worked out the most. Nowadays, the methods and methods of spiritual images acquired by the literature of previous centuries are widely used. But among them, the method of composition-storytelling (related to the change of "point of view" and the subject of the story) is beginning to take the lead.

Psychological analysis can be divided into internal (internal monologue, memory, associations and images of the imagination) and external, i.e. the author's speech, facial expressions, and other external manifestations of the psyche. Generally speaking, the writer expresses the fluctuations in the

inner world of the hero without interfering with the objective process of his feelings. Mental analysis has a complex character with attention to essence, and writers can use it to reveal the psyche of the hero, and interpreters (critic, researcher) can use the method of mental analysis (psychoanalysis) to examine the work of art.

In this sense, psychologism is a special quality of artistic form. At the same time, in some works (psychological novels), psychologism can be methodologically dominant. In such a case, not only the images of the characters, but also all other elements of the artistic form, i.e. the depicted world, artistic speech, composition, are subject to psychologism, as they form an aesthetic unity - style. In this regard, A. B. Esin defines psychologism as "methodical unity (integrity)". In this way, the artistic system of psychologism is the dominant method in the works, and the artistic form can cover all these three aspects and can be presented with various artistic tools and methods.

Modern philological science pays great attention to the role of emotional-emotional content, i.e. psychologism, in the structure of an artistic work. As noted by researchers and scientists, the speech of the speaker in the literary text is not simply given in accordance with existing language norms, but also depicted in an artistic state. At the same time, according to the image and rule, it includes in detail not only the state of verbal materiality of speech, but also the paralinguistic factors directly connected with it, that is, gestures, facial expressions and their instructions. Both this and that are described by words, which condition the transmission of paralinguistic code tools with linguistic code tools or the transition of one semiotic system to another. Some stylistic methods that allow the reader to witness the inner mental activity of the character are also an important aspect of the artistic text. The description of this process can be carried out in two ways, i.e. through the internal monologue, which takes place "without the intervention" of the author, and through the crosstalk of the author's and the character's voices in a quote that is not his own, and through the indirect speech of the author.

In the last quarter of the 19th century, the scientific direction of the psychological school emerged in the study of folklore and written literature. The founder of this trend is the German psychologist, philosopher and folklorist Wilhelm Wundt (1832-1920). The doctrine of the psychological state of the creator in the creative process forms the basis of this direction. Wundt was one of the first to investigate the creation of myths and poetic images. Wundt gives a great place to dreams and hallucinations in the creative process. A number of artists use his theory in creating their works. Wundt's theory has a great influence on Freud, the founder of Freudian psychology. According to him, the surrounding environment is regulated by the human mind. Artistic creativity is a product of the creator's mental state, and at the same time, the creative process enriches and deepens the human spiritual world. Some aspects of Wundt's theory are similar to some theories of other creators in terms of their subjective views on the issue of artistic creation, overestimation of the significance of symbolism and imagery in language and poetry.

So, representatives of the psychological school believe that the existing myths in the poetry and religious views of different peoples arose during different mental states of people, such as sleep, dreams or hallucinations. [12.262.] There are three types of internal speech in fiction, which are internal monologue, is an internal dialogue and an internal bite (replica). All of these together constitute a continuous process of internal communications of a person as a means of internal speech. [13.54.] Internal speech and its manifestations, in turn, serve to strengthen the psychologism of an artistic work. Also, the work is one of the main factors in revealing the psyche of its characters.

Each of the three forms mentioned above has its own structural and semantic features, which are manifested in the tasks that a person performs in the spiritual world. The simplest form of internal speech - an internal replica - a collection of unrelated words manifested in separate, short, non-speech-related processes, or an internal commentary of a person receiving external speech. [13.62] In short, an individual's emotional assessment of the receiving situation and situation requires an internal response. In turn, the object of assessment can be the whole situation itself or its part that has a strong impact on the psyche of the individual. Through the internal replica, the author reveals the mental state of the character at that very moment, i.e. surprise, love or hatred, joy or sadness.

A psychological artistic image is another type of inner speech - an inner dialogue, which is a sequence of opinions formed in the style of a dialogue. Internal dialogue is an imaginary conversation between two or more people, that is, one character speaks as two (sometimes more) characters at the same time. The second dialogue is an acute psychological state, in which a person splits into two phases - duality of personality. The third type of internal speech is an internal monologue, which is "the character's unmaterialized, self-directed and introspective speech; direct form of artistic psychology. It is conditionally accepted as a process of thought (feeling) that takes place in the human mind". direct internal monologue. If in mobile internal monologue, the character's inner thoughts are expressed through the author's speech, then in direct internal speech, the character's internal monologue is completely spoken in his own language, and in live speech, the existing construction is preserved. . Verbal abbreviations, phonetic copresences, many, question marks, exclamation marks and punctuation marks (pause tool), short sentences, repeated words, incomplete and illogical expressions, which describe the feeling more effectively.

Internal monologue, in turn, is divided into such types as monologue-discussion, monologue-memory, monologue-reflection, depending on what kind of information it conveys to the reader. If we get autobiographical and socio-psychological information about the character through monologue-memories, we will be able to understand his reaction to the outside world through monologue-discussion and monologue-reflection. In many cases, the concepts of internal monologue and stream of consciousness are put together by literary experts. For example, literary scholar D. Kuronov recognizes the stream of consciousness as the result

of effective research to depict mental processes as realistically as possible, using the possibilities of internal monologue as much as possible, and the fact that internal monologue does not appear to be conditioned by logic patterns. For realistic literature, it uses as synonymous terms. [15. 209]

One of the criteria that ensures artistic quality is the description of the psychological state of the characters. Studying the work of art from the point of view of psychologism helps to theoretically improve both literary studies and the science of psychology. The ability to create a vivid image of the heroes of the work is an important condition of artistry. By analyzing them psychologically, one can get a clear picture of the mental state of the creator and the heroes of the work.

Psychologist M.G. Yaroshevsky said that "...in the works of art, the perception of a person by a person and other mental processes, at the same time, not only the characters of the work, but also the character traits, behavior, thinking, inclinations and aspirations of the creator of the work, reflect [16.14] writes

In fact, when creating the characters of the work, the writer first imagines their actions, situations and aspirations, and then reflects them through the prism of the soul. Julian Barnes and Ulugbek Hamdam also put forward the idea that science should serve to human happiness. The reader is able to pay attention to the unusual events that can happen in life and society, along with them to the sacred and high feelings of human nature, which can change the environment beyond recognition. focuses on simple daily tasks.

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